

It has been demonstrated that the strong solvent specificity noted in the classical measurements is qualitatively explicable¹⁷ in terms of different solvent effects on different steps in the association process. It is then believed¹⁸ that all the following factors must be considered before a quantitative explanation of association in a system such as $MnSO_4-CH_3OH-H_2O$ can be offered: selective solvation of one or both ions, changing availability of a given solvent component due to strong solvent-solvent H-bonding interactions, and coupling of these two preceding factors. In the case of Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} ion, association with bicarbonate ion in H_2O , 5% $MeOH-H_2O$ and 10% $MeOH-H_2O$ could not be extended to a wider range of solvent mixture. It is of course desirable to carry out the investigation in a wider range but this could not be

Fig 3 $\log K_A$ vs $1/D$ for (○) $Ni(HCO_3)_2$, and (□) $Co(HCO_3)_2$.

done due to the very limited solubility in higher $MeOH$ content. However, the above three solvents allowed a reasonably good test for the solvent effect on K_A , in these two systems as an example for 2 : 1 salts. Fig. 3 show plot of $\log K_A$ vs $1/D$ for Co and Ni bicarbonates at 25° . It is seen that the linear behaviour is very well established in this low CH_3OH content range which agrees very well with data obtained earlier in 2 : 2 salts.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of Acid Hydrolysis of Nitrobenzoic Acid Hydrazides

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HYDRAZIDES have been hydrolysed in water under acidic, basic and neutral conditions. The detailed paths of the hydrolysis have been established by the use of various mechanistic criteria.

The acid catalysed hydrolysis of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid hydrazide, *p*-nitrobenzoic acid hydrazide and 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid hydrazide have been investigated at 90° (1-10 M H_2SO_4 , 1-9 M HCl , 1-6 M $HClO_4$). For the same molarity of the acids, the rates in sulphuric acid were found to be greater than those of HCl and $HClO_4$. Detailed kinetics study, using concepts such as ionic strength effect, solvent deuterium isotope effect, Bunnett and Arrhenius parameters showed that the conjugate acid species of the substrate undergo bimolecular nucleophilic attack of a water molecule on the carbonyl carbon of the hydrazide. The neutral species of hydrazide were found to be unreactive towards water as a nucleophile.

Experimental

m-Nitrobenzoic acid hydrazide, *p*-nitrobenzoic acid hydrazide, 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid hydrazide were prepared by the known method¹ and recrystallised from H₂O (m p 153°, 210° and 150°, respectively). Acid solutions of various strengths were made by appropriate dilutions of concentrated acids (A.R.). The ethanol used in solvent effect runs, was purified². The stated deuterium content of D₂O was higher than 99.4%. NaClO₄ was used to adjust the ionic strength. All other chemicals used were of A R grade.

All kinetic experiments were carried out in a thermostat ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). The reaction rates were determined spectrophotometrically using a SPEKOL ZEISS spectrophotometer set at 460 m μ . Initial concentration of hydrazides in the kinetic runs was $2.344 \times 10^{-4} M$ and the volume of total reaction mixture was 50 ml. The rate constants were measured from the appearance of hydrazine³.

Results

The rate constants were found to increase with increase in acid concentrations and did not reach a maximum. Keeping the reaction conditions similar, different runs were made taking different substrate concentrations. Pseudo-first order rate constants in the hydrazides are found to be independent of change in substrate concentrations; the rates never reached maximum in the case of hydrazides.

The systematic difference in the catalytic powers of the strong acids depends upon the reaction mechanism rather than the hydrazide structure. The acid catalysed rates for hydrolysis of hydrazides were found to decrease in the sequence, H₂SO₄ > HCl > HClO₄.

As has been done for the acid hydrolysis of benzoic acid hydrazide^{5,6} and *p*-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide⁷, the rate constants in the case of *p*-nitrobenzhydrazide, *m*-nitrobenzhydrazide and 3,5-dinitrobenzhydrazide were determined at the various acidities. Keeping the ionic strengths constant, the results show that the rate of hydrolysis increases steadily with the increase in stoichiometric acid concentration. From the linear plot of the rate coefficients against acidity at different ionic strengths, it can be calculated that (i) at each ionic strength, the observed rate constants *k* can be represented as

$$k = k_H + C_{H^+} \quad (1)$$

where, *k* and *k*_{H⁺} are observed and specific rate constants, (ii) the slopes of the lines (*k*_{H⁺}) decrease with the increase in ionic strength, the reaction exhibiting a negative ionic strength effect, and (iii) the reaction due to neutral species is absent as the lines of the graphs pass through origin⁸.

The rate constants calculated by equation (2) are totally matching with the experimental rate constants, indicating that it obeys the equation

$$k = k'_{H^+} H^+ \exp. (a\mu) \quad (2)$$

The values obtained for *K*'_{H⁺} and *a* are reported in Table 1, where *K*'_{H⁺} is the slope of linear plot between log *K*'_{H⁺} and μ , and *a* is an intercept at zero ionic strength.

TABLE 1—THE *k*'_{H⁺} AND *a* VALUES FOR EQUATION (2)

Substrate	<i>k</i> ' _{H⁺} × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹	<i>a</i> × 10 ² (M ⁻¹)
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHNH ₂	0.965	-3.93
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHNH ₂	1.175	-8.04
3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ CONHNH ₂	0.755	-0.851

The values of the Bunnett and Olsen (B.O.) parameters¹⁰ and the hydration parameter¹¹ are given in Table 2. These values were obtained from

TABLE 2—THE B.O. AND HYDRATION PARAMETERS FOR THE HYDRAZIDES

Substrate	B.O. Parameter			Hydration parameter
	HClO ₄	H ₂ SO ₄	HCl	
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHNH ₂	0.875	0.820	0.853	4.2
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHNH ₂	0.950	0.864	0.875	4.1
3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ CONHNH ₂	0.977	1.153	1.179	4.0

plots of (log *k* + *H*₀) vs (*H*₀ + log *H*⁺) and (log *k* + *H*_A) vs (log *a*_{H₂O})¹², respectively. Yates and other have tried to study this matter quantitatively. Accordingly we have plotted (log *k* + *H*_A) vs log *a*_{H₂O}. The results show that four water molecules are involved in this reaction.

A qualitative solvent effect was studied and it was found that the reaction rate decreases with increasing concentration of ethanol in case of all the hydrazides for the range of ethanol (v/v%) 0.00-40.00.

The reaction is a specific acid catalysed reaction involving prior equilibrium formation of the conjugated acid of the substrate similar to amides¹³ as indicated by the rate ratios *k*_{D₂O}/*k*_{H₂O} (1.825, 1.92 and 1.385 for *m* nitro-, *p*-nitro- and 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid hydrazides, respectively). The activation parameters in the temperature range 70-90° were determined by measuring the rate of hydrolysis in this range (Table 3).

Discussion

In case of hydrazides, the rate constants increase with the increase in acid concentration but did not reach a maxima probably due to their lower basicity as compared to that of the amides. The acid catalysed

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE ACID-CATALYSED HYDROLYSIS OF HYDRAZIDES AT 90°

Substrate	Acidic medium 6 M	E kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS [‡] e.u.	ΔH [‡] kcal mol ⁻¹	A min ⁻¹
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHNH ₂	H ₂ SO ₄	18.59	-26.28	18.29	3.467 × 10 ⁷
	HCl	18.33	-27.29	18.41	2.188 × 10 ⁷
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CONHNH ₂	H ₂ SO ₄	18.50	-26.78	17.87	6.607 × 10 ⁹
	HCl	18.61	-26.75	18.41	2.816 × 10 ⁷
3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ CONHNH ₂	H ₂ SO ₄	18.84	-26.38	14.42	3.311 × 10 ⁷
	HCl	17.46	-30.76	16.53	3.802 × 10 ⁹

The error in the value of log A, E, ΔS[‡] and ΔH[‡] are ± 0.6, ± 1.0 kcal mol⁻¹, 2.0 e.u. and 2.0 kcal mol⁻¹, respectively.

rates for the hydrolysis of hydrazides decrease in the order, H₂SO₄ > HCl > HClO₄. This order indicates that the reaction involves a nucleophilic attack of a water molecule upon carbonyl carbon via A-2 mechanism which is retarded by anions of low charge density such as perchlorates, but only slightly indented (if not even assisted) by anions of high charge density, such as sulphates or chlorides⁴. Thus, the order of catalytic effectiveness may be explained in terms of the order of ability of the anions in stabilising the intermediate.

The constant ionic strength effect is carried out in a mixture of HClO₄ and NaClO₄ for these hydrazides. These results are fitted in equation⁹, which is a modified Bronsted-Bjerrum equation applied to the conventional reaction scheme⁹. These calculated rate constants and experimental rate constants matching with each other indicates that the reaction proceeds *via* conjugate acid species of the substrate which is subject to a negative salt-effect. So this reaction can be presented as

where, S is a hydrazide and X[‡] is the transition complex.

The values of the Bunnett and Olsen (B.O.) parameters and hydration parameters (Table 2) indicate that the rate limiting step is the nucleophilic attack of a water molecule on the protonated substrate. The four water molecules observed here may be involved one for protonation and the second for nucleophilic attack on the protonated substrate. The other three water molecules may be concerned with protonation, proton transfer or processes which can not be specified. As the concentrations of ethanol increase the rate constants decrease. This is may be due to the polar character of the transition state.

It has been shown¹⁴ that the entropies of activation of a series of acid catalysed reactions which are known from other criteria to occur by SN¹ mechanism fall in the range +9 to +6.1 e.u. compared to -20.9 to -24.6 e.u. for a group of SN² reactions. This difference is presumably due to higher degree of orientation required for an attacking water molecule in the latter case (SN²) than a group of solvating water molecule in the

former case (SN¹). The values of various activation parameters (Table 3) support to SN² mechanism. Therefore, the probable reaction path consistent with the experimental data collected so far may be formulated as,

where, R = *m*-NO₂C₆H₄; *p*-NO₂C₆H₄; 3,5-(NO₂)₂C₆H₃.

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